

Abstract

Reincarnation and karma are discussed as equivalents to intrinsic energy oscillation (as postulated by Complete Relativity) and law of equal action and reaction (as postulated by Newton and generalized in Complete Relativity), respectively.

Details on soul (anima) oscillation inter-species and symbiosis of animarum and bodies of materialium are presented and discussed. Additional evidence for the existence of animae is also provided.

On reincarnation, karma and soul-body interactions

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1 Intro

Scale invariance of physical laws and relativity in everything (notably in particle/wave duality) enable recognition of principles of reincarnation and karma in laws of energy oscillation and equal action and reaction, respectively.

In Complete Relativity[1] (CR), these are not principles which may or may not be followed rather elementary (core) laws which must be satisfied over finite time [proportional to energy] to enable existence.

2 Karma

The law of equal action and reaction (3rd law of motion), devised by Newton, is well known. With Complete Relativity, however, it became obvious the law *needs* generalization.

Reaction cannot be absolutely instantaneous, but it is unavoidable over time, although some relativity in interacting bodies is implied too.

With scale invariance/self-similarity of universes (distinct forms of energy in this context), clearly even people must be nothing more but a distinct form of energy to a particular universe. And that energy, like all energy, must relatively oscillate, fluctuate and obey the principles of action and reaction on that particular scale.

With postulates of CR understood and accepted, karma and reincarnation are a manifestation of generalized action/reaction and energy oscillation, respectively.

Interaction between two individual life forms can thus be understood as n_{th} order interaction in CR.

Consider a person A throwing a piece of rock at person B. The interaction of a rock with a person B may be considered as 1st order interaction, with the rock being the force carrier particle.

But interaction between persons A and B is also real, as a 2nd order interaction (certainly, the person B will likely look at it as the 1st order interaction - considering A as a source of force, rather than the rock).

The intrinsic relativity of interaction order requires reaction on every level (order) of interaction over time/space.

Thus, eventually, a similar rock (or energy) will be thrown at person A too - from a person relatively equivalent to person B.

Here, one might wonder how variable is relativity here. This should be proportional to distance in time/space. Sometime the rock will be thrown immediately by the very *same* person B, sometimes not.

Note that in CR, everything changes all the time, so, in any case, reaction never comes from [absolutely] the same body acted upon! Nor can the reaction be absolutely equal to action - it evolves.

Generally, any distinct lifeform exists on different scales - on some scales relativity will be high, on some low.

In case of soul/body coupling, high relativity might generally exist in acting bodies (although reference frames will exist where these may be interpreted as the same bodies), but not in souls. Thus, it might seem that *justice* is not always preserved, however, if souls are allowed to reincarnate - it will be. And, in fact, the relativity in interactions requires the existence of soul and reincarnation.

While there should be no doubt that karma is real, one might wonder about its mechanics. In short - it must be diverse.

On the abstract level, one might consider that actions and reactions occur between field (action) potentials, which have certain capacity. With actions performed, capacitors get discharged. Reaction charges them.

In CR, there is no absolute causality - past and future are correlated and effectively attract each other. The reaction *equal* to action can be delayed but can, thus, also be a precursor to action.

In the example above, it is equally valid to say that person B attracted the rock throwing action (or, more precisely, difference of potentials reaching a particular threshold has triggered the action in that direction).

If information is preserved between incarnations, it obviously must be preserved in space, not in standard matter - such as that forming the bodies.

It should then be valid to assume that entanglement of souls is dependent on preserved information (capacitor states), which will then eventually (in some incarnation) result in entanglement mirroring the original one, hence producing the reaction.

In any universe, everything is remembered on some scale. There is no absolute forgiveness. One may only recognize relative forgiveness in delay of reaction during weak evolution when it may span multiple incarnations (body generations) of life.

Delays occur due to fragility of entanglement, spatial/temporal symmetries in entangled potentials and due to finite speed of action/reaction propagation, but it should be impossible to avoid karmic reactions.

Like everything, actions and reactions are quantized. Reaction to action can be fragmented into multiple quanta of smaller reactions separated in time or space, but opposite is also possible - multiple smaller reactions can fuse into bigger reaction (probability for fusion increases with the number of *pending* reactions).

I have hypothesized that, during strong evolution, as the local universe approaches the point of synchronization between space and time, delays of local karmic reactions should become shorter - with less relativity even in interacting bodies. Apparently, this can already be witnessed[2] in general precursors[3].

2.1 Current state of karma on Earth

Most human systems and [systems of] individuals around the world are more or less polarized. There is a lot of delay and polarization in karmic reactions between groups of people, but most delayed is the karmic reaction to abuse of Earth and its natural systems by human ego-systems.

It is, however, evident that we are accelerating toward the equilibrium state - karmic reactions are happening already and increasing in intensity. One can also see that reactions are fusing through positive feedback mechanisms. The acceleration is accelerating.

A good example of fused reactions is a devastating earthquake during the rise of COVID-19 pandemic in the capitol city of Croatia. While humans may consider them as problems and label as catastrophes, viruses, floods and earthquakes are not the problem, certainly not coincidences - for Earth and all life of Earth (including human!) these are the solution to restoration of balance. Someone else is the problem, and as long as this problem does not identify itself as a problem the problem will get bigger and the solution more extreme (reaction of Earth's immune system to human action).

3 Incarnation

Current incarnation of an individual always includes the body of matter and associated space rooted in the soul. Both contain genetic code, but they are entangled and co-evolve together in symbiosis.

An individual life begins in a moment of conception when the soul starts acquiring mass (more precisely - mass in the form of matter, as it already has some energy in the form of dark matter).

3.1 Two components of a soul

Each soul has two components - real and imaginary (img).

Img component is the gravitational maximum while real component is the induced maximum of acquired body of matter.

Real component will thus develop according to the DNA inherited from body ancestors, while img component develops with the execution of programming stored in DNA [equivalent] of the soul.

However, as these components co-evolve, one will effectively induce mutations in the other.

During lifetime of an individual, one of these may be dominant and other recessive in driving the evolution and expression of the individual, but, at any time, personality is a superposition of both. Generally, the expression of these will alternate during lifetime, resulting in significant personality changes although certain characteristics will always be preserved.

One will thus have periods in life when it will be expressing behaviour of its body ancestors (parents or grandparents), but also periods when it will be expressing behaviour of its soul ancestors, which are always different than the body ancestors and are not necessarily human.

If there is a large difference between soul personality and body personality, time in between will be experienced as a period of crisis - when the individual will be most insecure, questioning its own identity and be most prone to depression.

The oscillation is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Frequency of oscillation is different between species, but it also changes slowly during incarnation (not illustrated on Fig. 1).

The end of incarnation lifetime is the moment of death, when soul decouples from the body of matter. At that point, induced real soul component is deflated and/or dissolves into individual components of higher orders.

I hypothesize that, at times of strong evolution, personalities are synchronized and this is reflected in the body - it is effectively adjusted to the soul so this must include strong mutations (driven by horizontal gene transfer).

Note that body personality here is effective personality - the ecosystem of a body may behave as a single body but on its own it is not a conscious individual. The effective body personality thus must be a personality of

Figure 1: Personality oscillation

one quantum of the soul (souls have 2 quanta, one of which is dominant) whose personality better matches those of body ancestors (ie. parents). These quanta are oscillating in mass (energy) but due to high compression in space relative to the body this is a superposition in space, which is, in the body, expressed as superposition in time (ie. high parallelization of brain operation).

The frequency of this oscillation is high when the soul is not coupled with a body, however, with coupling the oscillation is extremely slowed down - rest mass of quanta and distance between them increases but this distance is still [interpreted as] 0 relative to distances between components of the body (real mass).

The quanta also oscillate horizontally (changing distance) between discrete energy levels (discontinuities).

A change of energy level can be unstable and lead to complete collapse of the soul (death) - all death events occur with instability on one of the discontinuities.

For us, these are discontinuities in time and they also oscillate and evolve between incarnations (reflected in lifestyle), but weakly - uncertainty in age is generally 1-2 years for mammals on Earth.

In my example[4], two major discontinuities are located at 35 and 50 years (or at least such is the hypothesis).

If I do not die around the age of 35 (I didn't, in current incarnation), I will certainly live up to the age of 50 (\pm uncertainty), but I'm unlikely to die at the age of 50 because the collapsing soul has to *stop* at the 35y discontinuity where it will remain for next 35 years (unless it is unstable, but this is less likely now) - giving a total lifespan of 85 years (\pm uncertainty).

The magnitude and nature of changes one will experience during energy

level changes, depends on the individual.

In my case, starting at the age of 35 (with a maximum possibly at age 36) I was experiencing very strong changes - overwhelming synchronicity and mental transformation (loss of polarization).

Something similar but of different magnitude should thus be happening to me around the age of 50.

There are also minor discontinuities but these are generally stable during growth (inflation), unstable during deflation.

Due to such mental changes, one should be able to sense when it is about to die, unless the magnitude of changes is extremely low.

While my major discontinuities may be at 35 and 50 years, on average these are different, possibly at 13 and 60 years (globally, average lifespan was 73 years in 2019.).

The stability of coupling of bodies and souls will depend on compatibility. Having a major discontinuity at 35 years, coupling of my soul with canine will be unstable and short-lived, while for general population this coupling will be more stable and even long-lived if indeed the first major discontinuity is roughly equal to canine lifespan.

In case of low compatibility, major discontinuities may be unreachable, while minor may become major discontinuities (implying the existence of even lower energy discontinuities than minor).

Note also that lifespan is changing for general (polarized) population (it was increasing so far, but should be decreasing now).

I believe that general population, being polarized, has photon souls, while some of us have [graviton] neutrino souls. While photon souls of Earth are slowly evolving into neutrino souls, temporary increase in polarization is expected during strong evolution events.

3.2 Lifespan of general population

In the previous chapter two discontinuities of the soul have been hypothesized that determine the lifespan of general population (those with photon souls).

While photon as a whole is electrically neutral, its two constituent quanta are charged and even though these charges may be low (most energy being gravitational) they will be sensitive to certain frequencies of electro-magnetic radiation.

I have hypothesized elsewhere that photon is a composite particle - in CR, no particle can be absolutely elementary, and there are no absolute bosons and fermions, only relative.

Note that, once coupled with the body, change in momenta likely results in decrease of angular frequency, while oscillation of mass could produce

orbitals and result in shielding, making one charge dominant (reflected in personality expression).

For photon souls it would be natural that these are sensitive to Earth's magnetic field to some degree.

Note that correlation between [changes in] Earth's magnetic field and human health has already been found in multiple studies[5].

At some field strength, splitting of energy levels (discontinuities) should occur and the magnetic field should be correlated with lifespan.

Figure 2: left) geomagnetic axial dipole strength⁶, right) life expectancy⁷

The strength of Earth's geomagnetic axial dipole and life expectancy over time are shown in Fig. 2.

The magnetic field data from 1840 to 2020 has then been inverted (flipped vertically) and vertically stretched to fit life expectancy data (although in this case rotation gives a better fit). This is shown in Fig. 3.

The red curve shows global life expectancy, green the inverse of magnetic field strength while blue is the same but phase shifted by 50 years.

Obviously, there is a strong correlation with IGRF-12 model in the period 1950 - 2000.

Interestingly, 50 years is not only the phase shift and length of period of strong correlation, it is also the arithmetic average lifespan in Fig. 3. [calculated as (min. lifespan + max. lifespan) / 2] and, what I consider, average human lifespan over the course of evolution.

Figure 3: Life expectancy / mf correlation

Mathematically, correlated lifespan (blue curve), assuming increasing divergence between mf and lifespan over time, can be expressed as:

$$\Delta T = [C_0 - B(t - t_0)] C_1 + C_2(t - t_1)$$

ΔT = expected lifespan
 B = magnetic field strength
 t_0 = phase shift = 50 years
 t_1 = year of divergence = 1840 + 50 = 1890

Note that data for life expectancy before year 1950 is scarce and the curve is the result of interpolation between distant points.
 Also, the data for recent years (shaded area) has some uncertainty (most people born during the period are still alive) and is likely to change.

From available data one can extrapolate possible discontinuities and their stability over time.

From 1770 to ≈ 1900 , average lifespan was 27 ± 1 or 35 ± 1 , depending on continent. This can be represented by two energy levels - E_{13} (maximum lifetime of 13 y) and E_{22} (maximum lifetime of 22 y), as shown on Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Lifespan correlated energy levels

Here, energy levels should be understood as orbital periods. Due to general oscillation, periods (lifetimes) on a particular energy level are quantized by [more] elementary periods.

Note that each level has maximum capacity and lifespan is a sum of lifetimes spent on each level.

The two levels are likely the result of splitting of a 19 y period level (E_{19}). Initially the two levels were roughly the same, but one was unstable giving a maximum lifespan of 38 years (this is consistent with DNA records[8]).

The splitting is not symmetric as both levels are orbitals of the same gravity source. Thus, the former E_{19} level period is at $2/3$ the distance between E_{13} and E_{22} periods.

The evolution of these energy levels should probably be correlated with evolution of inner planets. Here, splitting of energy levels should be correlated with [breaking of] orbital resonances.

Note that difference in orbital period at Earth's distance from the Sun and Mars' perihelion distance is equal to orbital period of Venus. This probably indicates that Venus and Mars were in resonance (1:2) at time Earth was created, implying that Earth was created at Venus' orbit (or out of Venus) and then started drifting away. Mars, entangled with Earth, drifted away for the same distance leaving original entanglement with Venus fossilized in perihelion (relative to Earth).

But from the Sun's reference frame, it was likely that Venus separated more from Earth/Mars than these drifted away from the Sun.

Note that orbital period at Mars' perihelion is roughly at $2/3$ the distance between Earth's orbital period and current Mars' orbital period.

The energy level E_{22} was unstable in Africa and Asia and remained as such until ≈ 1925 . The two levels give maximum lifespan of $2 \cdot 13 + 22 = 48$ years. Thus, at some point one or both levels had to split, and/or the oscillation was excited and a *higher* level became available, to enable larger lifespans.

Note that splitting of energy levels is generally associated with increasing magnetic field strength, not decreasing. Thus, if any splitting occurs here it is not directly caused by changes in the global magnetic field rather local increase in polarization - which must be synchronized (negatively correlated in this case) with the global magnetic field.

However, continuous increase in orbits (orbital periods) can be a direct consequence of a global decrease in magnetic field strength - assuming that constituent photon (soul) quanta gyrate around the magnetic field line of the global field.

The phase shift of 50 years should probably be interpreted as the time required for these changes to be incorporated into body DNA and reflected in epigenome. It is thus the phase shift between the soul and the body.

Lifespan is DNA coded and, theoretically, one should not only be able to derive lifespan from DNA, but by comparison of encoded lifespan with encoded lifespans in past generations (adjusted for its periodic variation per Fig. 3) and by matching other DNA characteristics, one should be able to find its past incarnations or at least potential candidates (though, for relevant certainty one will probably need to compare the personal lives of individuals).

Typically, in polarized human society, increase in lifespan is credited to humans - *improvements* in medical care, diets, lifestyle, etc.

However, these changes are likely only synchronized with increase in lifespan and cannot affect lifespan significantly - maximum effect is probably the deviation in lifespan oscillation between incarnations (a couple of years at most).

Consider vaccination - it is commonly believed it saves human lives, but the need for this saving is the result of cancerous nature, does it then increase human lifespan or is it just a way to sustain it in societies that live separate from nature but commonly invade it (and pick up viruses when they do so)?

Isolated tribes may live shorter than civilized society but generally not by decades and not because they lack medicine - they die because they are less and less isolated from us, we introduce our diseases to them, we decrease their freedom, we are killing them and decreasing their gene pool.

Their souls might be programmed to live just as long as ours, but their bodies just can't adopt fast enough to such invasion. On top of that, they are probably not so obsessed about living into old age as zombies on drugs so they refuse our *medicine*. Unlike cancerous people, healthy people do not want to force life at any cost. Your lifespan may be 73 years, but how many years did you actually feel alive and not slaving to products and practices that sustain or are supposed to sustain your *life*? In any case, even if maximum possible lifespan continues increasing (as

suggested by Fig. 3), I do not expect for the average lifespan to follow - karmic reactions should be affecting souls and bodies at an accelerating pace during strong evolution.

Since average humans should be converging to homo.gamma (typically, a superposition of human and canine life forms), the average lifespan should be decreasing and will probably stabilize somewhere in the middle, perhaps at 50 years (ie. arithmetic average of soul lifespans of 13 and 87 years), or, more likely, at 43 (13 and 73 average) or 38 (13 and 63 average) years.

3.3 Coupling and genetic mutations

Genetic mutations are not random. Incompatibilities between the soul and a body may be associated with such mutations. For instance, a dominantly male soul coupled with a female body might *make* the individual homosexual and some clues may be imprinted in the genetic code of the body (although, synchronicity might be applied here, making cause and effect relative).

Note 1:

With population increase there is a greater chance of male/female body and soul coupling. This is one way to limit the population in order to maintain natural balance, but is also one of the ways to maintain the number of individuals required for neurogenesis[9]. Surface population size at times of major extinctions is not random - it corresponds to number of neuron cells/proteins which will be differentiated from surface cells/proteins and incorporated into mantle layers.

Note 2:

Genetic imprints associated with homosexuality may also be present in heterosexuals where they will induce stronger sexual desire which can result in population increase, but this also increases probability of homosexual descendants due to inherited genes.

Note 3:

No soul or body is 100% male or 100% female and thus no individual is 100% male or 100% female.

Incompatible couplings and genetic mutations are often a manifestation of karmic reactions, causing disorders and diseases.

3.4 Soul order

A 1st order soul is the primary or root soul, one that couples with matter of an individual at time of conception.

However, as particles (life forms) of a body of matter are also mutually in symbiosis, bodies of matter will be [unconsciously] coupling to, and co-evolve with, their own souls (particles -> molecules/microorgan[ism]s -> organs..).

Souls of organs may be considered as secondary souls. However, these couplings are not limited to two or three orders, although, effectively, they will be - ie. 1st order soul may not feel directly influenced by souls of the 4th order and beyond.

Note that 2nd order souls generally revolve around the 1st order soul, 3rd order souls revolve around 2nd order souls (as in planetary systems), etc. However, if the organism is evolving in a strong gravitational potential of a 3rd body, revolutions may be subdued and souls (or at least *their* bodies) might become locked in place between the 1st order soul and a 3rd body.

In such cases, depending on the strength of gravitational potentials, nth order bodies may develop in space in between and the whole system may form a compact organism of irregular structure.

However, considering the asymmetry in influence between a brain and other organs, it is possible that souls (being of lower energy scale) do still revolve around the primary soul (mental revolutions) and are only periodically coupling with organs.

Consider the heart - suppose it is pulsing at 76 bpm (beats per minute), this would imply an 2nd order soul is coupling and decoupling (through spin change) with the heart 76 times in every minute.

This should then be interpreted as periodic loss of consciousness of the heart, but one which doesn't have strong influence on the system - it has evolved to live synchronized with such pulsing of the heart.

It is obvious now why heart failure increases with obesity. If an organ next to the heart is concentrating mass but heart doesn't change in mass, this will affect the orbit of the heart's soul and may even cause the heart's soul to couple with a soul of that organ (perhaps periodically at the beginning, not causing death) or get ejected out of the system - causing system imbalance and a change of momentum of other souls, leading to death.

Note that this implies that heart should generally beat at a faster rate when closer to the primary soul.

If soul orbits follow gravitational orbital law, one can establish a relation between heart/brain distance, heart rate and soul gravitational mass. For precise results, one needs to know where exactly the heart's [primary] soul is. Most likely it is not in the centre of a heart, rather in the sinoatrial node - where heart impulse starts. Ie. assuming the same soul is alternating between human and blue whale (*B. musculus*) body species,

knowing the distance (r) from primary soul location (presumably brain centre) and heart soul location for both species, and knowing human rest heart rate (f_h), one can calculate rest heart rate of a blue whale (f_w) oscillation *soul mate*:

$$f = \frac{1}{T} = \frac{v}{2\pi r} = \frac{\sqrt{GM}}{2\pi\sqrt{r}r}$$

For human:

$$\sqrt{GM} = f_h * 2\pi\sqrt{r_h}r_h$$

r_h = distance between human brain centre and the heart

The equivalence of souls is the equivalence of GM products. The heart rate of a whale is then:

$$f_w = \frac{\sqrt{GM}}{2\pi\sqrt{r_w}r_w} = f_h \frac{\sqrt{r_h}r_h}{\sqrt{r_w}r_w}$$

r_w = distance between whale primary soul centre and heart soul centre

For an adult $f_h = 76 \text{ bpm} / 60 \text{ s} = 1.2666' \text{ Hz}$ (my rest heart rate), $r_h = 0.38 \text{ m}$ and assuming $r_w = 2 \text{ m}$:

$$f_w = 6.29 \text{ bpm}$$

From the above, one can also obtain the GM product for such soul.

Note however, that this GM product practically has no [physical] meaning in space U_0 (for standard $G = G_0$, it gives mass $4 * 10^{10} \text{ kg}$, equal to mass of the 99942 Apophis asteroid). The force (or curvature of space) associated with this product only affects particles of U_{-1} scale (souls) because soul space is of U_{-2} scale.

Particles can, effectively, only interact with particles of adjacent vertical energy levels (scales). Thus, even though standard atoms (U_0 scale) can couple with souls, they can't feel their gravity, at least not as physical force.

Note also that this implies that heart rate is correlated with passage of time for an individual soul - it scales proportionally to speed of time.

In other words - we feel gravity of our souls as time, a non-physical (mental) phenomena on standard scale. As an interesting side note - a hypothetical heart for a soul GM equal to Earth's GM would at Earth's surface radius beat once every 84.35 minutes. Note also that, even if organs do not effectively feel gravity of the souls, their masses could still be proportional to GM product of their souls. This would imply information exchanges through channels of entanglement and/or that some gravity does *leak* to larger scale. Total amount of gravity that does leak would then be proportional to GM and equal to acquired mass

(matter energy). With acquired mass, leaked gravity would be shielded or, equivalently, return to the source (equilibrium).

In that case, the primary soul that oscillates between human and whale bodies must be in excited state while *in* the body of a whale.

Assuming blue whale brain mass of 6 kg and human brain mass of 1.4 kg, for the example above, whale rest heart rate would then be:

$$f_w = \sqrt{\frac{6}{1.4}} 6.29 \text{ bpm} = 13.03 \text{ bpm}$$

This appears to be in agreement with measurements - heart rates during shallow, short-duration dives typically associated with rest have been measured to be 13 bpm (for a ≈ 70000 kg, 23 m long blue whale)[10].

However, I do not have any reliable data on brain/heart distance for blue whales - r_w is an estimate I came up with consulting various literature, and r_h is an estimate based on my own measurements, so ratio between r_h and r_w could be somewhat different, although probably not much.

However, it is not necessary for heart's soul itself to be orbiting, a smaller soul quantum (which is, essentially, a quantum of momentum or kinetic energy) may instead be orbiting the primary soul and be periodically absorbed by the heart's soul (relatively equivalent to the photon momentum absorption by an atomic electron) - in that case heart's soul only periodically changes its energy level.

Note that this does not imply that organs do not have an orbital momentum relative to the primary soul - it may only be extremely slowed down in time (nth order space) with growth during incarnation (note that embryos do noticeably rotate).

At the beginning of life, img component of the soul is unstable and after initial inflation it likely collapses again to smaller scale.

However, *orbiting* real mass [induced real component of the soul] is rapidly growing and will be slowly inflating the img component (or be synchronized with growth of the img component).

At some moment during *middle age*, two components will be in balance and body will stop growing.

That moment is synchronized with death of another individual (typically relative, during equilibrium conditions in environment) when emitted quantum of momentum with the soul collapse of that individual will be temporarily absorbed by the img component, causing its rapid inflation.

At that point, to conserve total momentum of the soul system, real component starts decreasing momentum, generally radius (synchronized with the shrinking of the body of matter), albeit at extremely slow rate for human [alike] individuals.

Note that inflation of the img component can be interpreted as increase in

density of space (dark matter).

3.4.1 Strong evidence in lonely hearts

In the previous chapter, I have hypothesized secondary souls orbit around the primary. While the model may give good results for heart rates, is it real?

Hearts can still beat in a jar, so that seems like a good argument against the hypothesis, as there is no primary soul to orbit around.

However, this is solved with momentum conservation and can actually be interpreted as evidence that organs in a network of an organism are a result of *fossilization* of symbiosis between organisms.

Suppose that beating of a heart in a jar is correlated with its soul spin momentum (which might still include periodic inflation/deflation of the soul - loss of consciousness). It is entirely possible that this momentum gets converted to orbital momentum at time of entanglement with a more massive soul (like primary human soul).

Note that such conversions of momentum were happening with Solar System planets during inflation, as my Solar System analysis has shown.

In that case, it is not the location of a heart that determines its beat rate, rather the location of the heart in an organism was predetermined by the heart rate.

Interestingly, assuming that at time of death, heart's soul decouples travelling at the speed of light, it would take 0.13353 seconds to orbit around the Earth's surface.

If one allows the soul to couple with the dying heart with each orbit again, the heart would beat at a maximum 450 bpm (probably lower as soul absorption and emission is not instant).

This is exactly the maximum heart rate reported during ventricular fibrillation - measured heart rates are 350 - 450 bpm[11].

During this time, heart does not pump blood, and, if left untreated, death occurs within a couple of minutes. Impulses during atrial fibrillation are also 350 - 450 bpm.

This, certainly, could be interpreted as evidence for soul-body coupling and evidence that our souls are indeed *static* photon or neutrino like quanta of Earth's space (if this particle would not be a part of Earth's space it would radiate away rather than orbit, due to velocity exceeding gravitational escape velocity of Earth).

While our hearts likely cannot beat faster than 450 bpm, hearts of some mammals (like that of pygmy shrew) can and do beat at much faster rates.

However, there is a large difference between a rest heart rate and rate during fibrillation - in former, soul is strongly coupled to the body, in the latter

soul orbits the Earth, only weakly coupling as a precursor to death (strong decoupling).

This could be experimentally verified, as this implies that, even if the rest heart rate of some mammal is higher than 450 bpm, its rate during fibrillation could not be higher than 450 bpm (assuming all mammals have equivalent souls).

Note that this also implies that, in case there are no significant differences in orbital eccentricity, fibrillation heart rate depends on heart's distance from Earth's centre.

Also, this shows that orbits of uncoupled souls do not follow orbital (Kepler's) law, which is then good evidence for dark matter being made of uncoupled souls, as hypothesized previously (dark matter in galaxies doesn't follow orbital law).

However, what is the mechanism preventing soul escape from Earth's gravity once it decouples from the body?

This can simply be its energy. The effective range of a force carrier particle is equal to Compton wavelength. Once emitted particle reaches maximum distance it would simply fall back to Earth.

In this case, required Compton wavelength is $2R\pi/2$, where R is Earth's radius. Required soul mass for that range is:

$$M_p = \frac{\hbar}{\lambda_\tau c} = \frac{\hbar}{R\pi c} = 1.7575 * 10^{-50} \text{ kg}$$

$$\lambda_\tau = \frac{1}{2} \frac{60}{450} c = 666.666 * 10^{-4} c = R\pi$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hbar &= 1.054573 * 10^{-34} \text{ Js} = \text{reduced Planck's constant} \\ c &= 2.99792458 * 10^8 \text{ m/s} = \text{speed of light} \\ R &= \text{Earth's radius} \end{aligned}$$

However, photon quanta oscillate between 3 generations (in my hypotheses) and this mass corresponds to heaviest generation, lightest mass is on the order of 10^{-54} kg and this would correspond to a heart rate of $6 * 10^{-2}$ bpm. Such heart rates have been measured in reptiles during hibernation (ie. common turtles[12]), suggesting relative equivalence of states of hibernation and heart fibrillation.

Note that photon mass determined in experiments indeed ranges from 10^{-50} kg to 10^{-54} kg[13].

However, note also that this is the effective mass of the photon - it can be interpreted as rest mass, but relative to an absolute rest frame (c).

This mass is the result of high spin momenta - orbiting rest mass within the photon ranges from 10^{-69} to 10^{-73} .

Using energy/mass/frequency equivalence, obtained mass corresponds to

a photon of the following frequency:

$$f = \frac{E}{h} = \frac{M_p c^2}{h} = \frac{450}{60\pi} = \frac{7.5}{\pi} = 2.387 \text{ Hz}$$

Interestingly, this is on the order of Schumann frequencies[14] (Earth's magnetic field resonant frequencies). In fact, the 6th harmonic is 14.3 Hz, equal to one of Schumann frequencies[15].

Living beings and living environments co-evolve and this correlation is not surprising.

The question is - why is photon range sometimes limited by effective mass and sometimes by its [orbital] rest mass (in which case, its range is the radius of the observable universe)?

The answer must be in coupling (entanglement), most likely, the effective photon mass is converted to rest mass (decreasing spin momenta) when it is coupled to a living being.

In this case, this is the coupling of a photon with [real mass of] Earth.

Even though there is a large difference in mass between the two groups of photons, they should not be generally considered as absolutely different species, rather same species on different vertical energy levels - I generally refer to massive photons as *static* photons forming space of a gravitational maximum. These are, together with *static* graviton neutrinos, carrier particles of large scale neutral (gravitational) and electro-magnetic fields (ie. fields of stars and planets).

Lower mass photons (10^{-69} - 10^{-73}) and graviton neutrinos are carrier particles of these fields on small scale (ie. fields of electrons and protons).

Since all large scale (*complex*) life is coupling with large scale gravitons (souls), the number of *vacant* souls for such forms of life should decrease exponentially with distance from the maximum.

4 Reincarnation

Reincarnation is oscillation in matter content coupled with the soul. A soul reincarnates at the moment of death when it decouples from the current body, couples with another and starts acquiring new mass in the form of matter.

Soul evolves together with matter, so even though one might refer to past lives of a particular soul, such references are conditional, the soul evolves from past lives just as the body evolves from the bodies of parents and grandparents.

I was me yesterday, but today my self is something else...

A body, like soul, has its own past lives.
No one will refer to the life of its parent or grandparent (up to the moment of conception) as its own past life, but it effectively is the past life of the body and each body will at certain times in life relive some moments of these past lives in, more or less, compressed form (just like the soul will relive some moments of its own past lives in compressed form).
All of, and entanglement with, these past lives, relative to the individual, decay, as current life evolves.

Nikola Tesla correctly deduced that people are [large scale] photons. Complete Relativity shows that people and all life of large scale in general must be a corpuscular manifestation of an oscillating energy.

Since everything is relative, so is determinism. From our perspective it might seem that life on Earth evolved by pure luck and that evolution is simply optimization for survival with no specific goals (targets). Once it becomes obvious that Earth is an evolving life form and, relative to Earth, we are its proteins, it becomes clear that our evolution is scripted.

It is also obvious that evolution involves at least 3 parties - life form(s), environment and a medium in which their interaction is embedded, and all these parties are relatively alive.

Evolution is thus always symbiotic - one might be adopting to environment but it is also changing the environment. One might be also adopting to the medium but one is affecting it too.

Life forms and environments are proteins and cells, while the medium is a personal space of a life form. It becomes obvious that this space, characterized by its gravitational maximum(s), must form the soul space of a living creature.

And this is where *invisible* phenomena are manifested - feelings.

Some might argue that feelings are the result of excretion of hormones, but that's the equivalent of saying that excretion of tears causes sadness rather than the other way around.

In any case, feelings and hormone excretion are two separate phenomena, manifested in two different domains.

What is cause and what is effect here, however, is relative - this is an synchronized interaction of multiple entities (phenomena) operating on two different levels of reality.

Compare this to oscillating electric and magnetic fields reinforcing each other - qualitatively, there is not much difference.

Space has memory (gravitational waves and *dark matter* prove that) so it is obvious that, once matter decouples from space, the memory remains on some level (scale).

Upon death, em waves and matter decay in a relative explosion, resulting in body fragmentation, providing food for construction and maintenance of other bodies.

At the same time, space is compressed in a relative implosion, resulting in fusion of gravitational maximums. It remains then in *hibernation* until it becomes the point of relative corpuscular annihilation when it inflates (conserving momentum), defusing into individual maximums (future organ souls).

If personal space of a human animal is formed with inflation of a quantum (*static* photon/neutrino) of Earth's space - a gravitational field line (orbital) collapsed to orbiting spin momentum, it becomes clear that the same quantum will get coupled with different bodies over time.

Each life form is thus not only the product of coupling of parental DNA and characteristics stored in space of merging gametes, but also coupling of this interaction with the 3rd party medium it is embedded in.

Consider a soul in a canine body which was previously in human body - the soul will drive the body to evolve human characteristics, while the body will drive the soul to subdue human characteristics and evolve canine.

Such coupling will at first be very unstable and short-lived (decoupling may occur already at embryonic stage), however, over multiple generations, two species will become more and more similar and new species will be formed - a chimera of original species.

Thus, oscillatory soul coupling between different species of bodies in symbiosis will effectively result in horizontal gene transfer between species.

Horizontal gene transfer, when a species receives genes from another species and incorporates them into its own DNA, is known to occur between bacteria, while it is highly uncommon between multicellular organisms.

However, recently, horizontal gene transfer has been discovered, for the first time, from a plant to an animal[16].

Note that, by currently accepted theories, genes normally transfer only vertically from parents to offspring, so it is believed that horizontal transfers happen very rarely and just by chance when, accidentally, one gene from one species ends up in another.

However, such reasoning is a consequence of uniformitarianism based on experience of weak evolution, where vertical transfer is a dominant gene transfer method.

Discarding randomness, this becomes a good evidence for soul oscillation - as hypothesized, soul has its own DNA equivalent co-evolving with a body, enabling horizontal gene transfer between species.

The soul genome [difference] may be considered as a blueprint for evolution (mutations) of body DNA, however, something has to physically alter the host body DNA. I consider viruses to be viable candidates as carrier particles of soul-body synchronicity, triggering these gene mutations.

Discovered horizontal transfer between a plant and an animal may be, at this point, considered an extremely rare accident of a gene transport by a virus, however, during strong (time compressed) evolution, such horizontal transfers between species should become more common, accelerating growth in frequency with evolution, and at its peak, likely even displacing vertical transfer as a common gene transfer method.

4.1 Oscillation

Each soul has a relatively discrete amount of energy, it co-evolves with bodies and its coupling with species of bodies (eco-systems) will generally not be random.

As [the soul of] particles inside the atom oscillates, human soul will oscillate too between different energy levels.

The period of time soul spends on each level is, in equilibrium, relatively constant (evolves slowly) - incarnations oscillate between relatively fixed lifetimes.

Frequency of oscillation changes with changes in the 3rd party medium - in this case, Earth.

High divergence is thus expected only in events of strong evolution - transformation of species through accelerated evolution, when soul *settles* into another equilibrium, oscillating in a different energetic setting (environment).

Note also that time of death is programmed to high precision, whether it is considered sudden, violent or occurring with old age. If a soul oscillates between 84 and 35 years in human lifespan, death in the latter will likely be violent.

This would be the equivalent of standard [horizontal] energy level changes of atomic electrons in QM. In such oscillation there is no change in species (average mass on each level), however, the state of particles (planets) in the Solar System shows that particles can oscillate in mass (lepton oscillation, vertical) with no change in horizontal energy level.

In that case (mass change), a soul will couple with different species of bodies, evolving in the same environment. Here, soul may even invert polarity (reflected

in extro/intro intelligence ratio) preserving lifespan between species, but with a large difference in mass.

I have hypothesized that my soul generally oscillates between human incarnations of ≈ 84 y and ≈ 35 y with roughly equal mass. But in any of these levels, it may also oscillate vertically in mass, in which case the soul may oscillate between whale incarnations - ie. *Orcinus orca* (lifespan 35 years) and *Balaenoptera musculus* (lifespan 84 years), or even between whale in one level and human in the other.

Note that oscillation of *human* souls on a planet surface seems to be entangled with energy levels and mass oscillation of planets in the Solar System.

Assuming my soul is vertically entangled with Mars' soul, oscillation between human form (76 kg mass) and blue whale (oscillation *soul mate*) form of 67240 kg is equivalent to difference in mass between Mars and Saturn.

This vertical entanglement of souls is further confirmed comparing the maximum size of a largest mammal on Earth with largest *mammal* of the Solar System - Jupiter.

The mass of Jupiter is 3.34 times Saturn's mass, this would give a maximum mass of 224686 ($3.34 * 67240$) kg for the largest mammal on Earth's surface (blue whale), agreeing very well with recorded and estimated maximum sizes for blue whales. Note that this implies that, if one does not consider Jupiter and Saturn bodies to be of the same species (although they are closely related - both are in 2e configuration, according to my Solar System analysis), then one might consider that there are two species of blue whales - those that reach 23 m and ≈ 70 tons, and those that might reach 33 m and ≈ 230 tons. However, as ≈ 23 m is also the length when they reach [sexual] maturity, rather than belonging to two different species, the point of maturity might be considered as a milestone (discontinuity) in evolution. Relatively, Jupiter species evolve from Saturn species, and that particular *moment* of strong evolution is fossilized as the point when it now reaches maturity.

Note that Saturn radius is fossilized as discontinuity in Jupiter - stripping the outer layer of molecular hydrogen gives Saturn radius.

Fossilization generally occurs in violent events. Strong evolution events may be relative extinction events but they are also life transformation events. And life transformation generally includes transfer to a place where conditions are favourable for new life. Thus, Jupiter too, was not formed where it is now. Comparing Mars with Luna (Moon) is [among mammals] equivalent to comparison between humans and some monkeys or smaller dogs.

Difference in mass between Mars and Venus/Earth is equal to difference between humans and cattle (domesticated/wild) or bottlenose dolphins.

It is thus most likely that these are the species *human* soul may oscillate between. Introverted and [environ]mentally conscious souls are more likely to oscillate between wild animal forms (neutral homo, whales, ..), while others are more likely to oscillate between domesticated animal forms (polarized homo, dogs, cows, ..).

Note that outer planets are more evolved than inner planets, making whales more evolved than humans. Quite likely, these species are significantly more intelligent than humans, albeit they have lost most of capability for external expression of intelligence. Not only that, but through soul oscillation, they evolve the intelligence in humans - introversion in humans likely has a source in whales, although it is still only a precursor to real introversion (we still have means for external expression).

A soul may couple with *non-compatible* species of bodies in between (probability for coupling of a particular soul and body is inversely proportional to distance in space/time between death and conception, and proportional to compatibility), but for much shorter amount of time than the average lifespan of the species (death will occur sooner due to incompatibility).

Soul thus has affinity for certain characteristics of bodies - which are DNA coded.

If souls and bodies co-evolve, both mental and physical characteristics should be more or less preserved between incarnations. Although, one must take into account evolution, some characteristics evolve weakly (especially during periods of weak evolution of the planet/environment).

While coupling is not perfect, one can expect significant preservation of strong (identity defining) characteristics between incarnations in bodies of same species, such as:

- blood type,
- physique (somatotype),
- sex/gender,
- intelligence amount and extro/intro ratio,
- etc.

Note that coupling of bodies and souls and oscillation of dominance between soul components explains why identical twins diverge in personality over time[17].

Some hypothesize that this occurs due to changes in epigenome, however, these changes are at most synchronized with this oscillation.

4.1.1 Details

Souls (*static* photons/neutrinos) generally oscillate between 3 generations[18], but this can be reduced to a two-body oscillation due to large difference in energy.

This oscillation will also oscillate between oscillation in space (mass) and time (lifespan) - one may be dominant. If mass stays relatively constant, oscillation is time dominant.

For an effective two-body oscillation, soul will effectively oscillate between two lifespans but with no change in species (ie. reincarnation between human bodies with lifespans of 85 and 35 years).

Mass is always a superposition - in time dominant oscillation, this is a superposition of two bodies of the same species.

During weak evolution, oscillation is generally time dominant, however, during strong evolution gene transfer becomes dominantly horizontal and mass becomes superposition of different species (a superposition of oscillation in time).

In CR, I have deduced the equation for soul acceleration at time of emission (decoupling):

$$a = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{c^3}{\hbar} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \phi \right) \Delta M \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{f^2}{f_n^2}}}$$

$$\Delta M^2 = 2^2 \frac{M_1^2 + M_2^2}{2} = 2 (M_1^2 + M_2^2)$$

Here, the type of oscillation is specified as a mixing angle (φ) and ΔM .

The angle represents the polarization while ΔM represents superposition of mass.

During weak (non-polarized) evolution, the mixing angle is generally 90° and M_1 is generally equal to M_2 (superposition of equal species in space/time).

However, during strong evolution, angle decreases and ΔM becomes superposition of different species.

Note that polarization is generally proportional to bias and thus inversely proportional to intelligence. It is electro-magnetic at some level and it is probably necessary to *guide* species to the south pole and further into mantle during the hypothesized planetary neurogenesis.

Thus, for most individuals it will probably be temporary (effectively limited to period of strong evolution).

Human intelligence has generally reached its peak and is currently declining[19]. This is yet another evidence that we are in a period of strong evolution.

I have hypothesized elsewhere what [superposition of] species the general population is evolving into (homo.gamma[20]).

Thus, human intelligence will continue declining at an accelerated pace until it becomes a superposition of human and typical domestic animal

intelligence (generally canine).

Current high polarization (vaxxers, anti-vaxxers, flat-earthers, mainstream religious fanatics...) of society and its delusions are just a precursor of a collapse of civilization, which will be increasingly concentrating on shorter and shorter short-term interests.

However, certain number of individuals is not polarizing and may even be decreasing polarization (increasing intelligence). This is generally valid for any strong evolution event - certain percentage of population is always immune to strong evolution (this creates diversity which is essential for life).

4.2 Experience of past lives

The individual will inevitably, in some way, re-live strongly imprinted moments from past lives in compressed form. For a body this re-evolution is typical and strongest during embryonic stage of development, for a soul this will generally be happening during the post-natal stage of development.

Because soul and body are strongly coupled during incarnation, evolution of both is synchronized. Therefore, affinity for certain characteristics should exist in coupling of souls and bodies.

Probability for a coupling of a forming or available body and a free soul is an exponential function of distance and compatibility (the ratio of attractive to repulsive quanta).

The greater is the difference in evolution of a body and a soul, the harder the life will be for both. The matching is governed by karma.

Differences between individuals arise due to different lifetimes in specific forms. Souls that spend a lot of time in non-human forms of lower (less evolved) energy are those who evolve slowly and resist progressive evolution while in human form. Compression of previous lives is low for such incarnations.

However, the presence of human form in oscillation accelerates evolution in less evolved forms and human form (or generally any more evolved form in energy oscillations) may thus be interpreted as one driver of evolution in these forms.

Body forms (species) in the chain of soul oscillation will depend on strength of entanglement between species.

4.2.1 Memory of soul's past lives

These memories must be imprints in space on a specific scale (a *sub-space*, such as time). Although specific memory can be effectively erased on one scale it is always present at some scale. The ability to read such memories depend on the strength of the imprint, its distance in time (space) and nature of the individual.

Possibility for conscious retrieval of such memories is highest for introverted species while for extroverted ones some possibility might exist if the brain is isolated from external stimulation.

For extroverted species, most of this reading happens unconsciously during embryonic (introverted) stage of development when the information is rewritten and used for the formation of instinct.

Possibility to retrieve sequential images (*trailers*) of the events is extremely low during the extroverted stage of life and these may only play out during sleep as a specific type of a dream (retro-vision). Such dreams may be recognized by the following characteristics:

- characters are unknown - do not exist in current life of the dreamer (although this is not a requirement - depends on the brain pattern matching and correlation system),
- dreamed event is the one which would leave a strong imprint (death, generally),
- dream is interrupted not at the moment of death, but shortly after the soul leaves the body,
- blank visuals (due to the inability of a brain to match the information with experience in current incarnation),
- a strong feeling of a different identity in the dreamed event.

Out of body experiences and dreams of deaths of past incarnations seem to imply that a soul has an audio/visual system of its own, but this is not necessarily the case.

Death cannot be absolutely instant - it must be gradual. That is why every lifeform is a composition of multiple lifeforms.

Human organs (introverted organisms), for example, do not all fail (die) at once, simultaneously.

First, the human being as a distinct lifeform dies, but the *brain being* is still alive and the soul is still coupled to the brain. Once the brain dies, the soul might still be coupled to some smaller organism within the brain. The life continues collapsing through smaller and smaller organisms until it is small enough to float away from the body.

But even at that point, as experiences suggest, the soul could still be entangled with the body and, in that case, the human being can be revived as a distinct lifeform again.

Thus, it is not necessary for the soul itself to have any audio/visual systems, it only has to have memory.

In fact, if the collapse to naked soul is not complete before the soul is coupled to another body, it is not required for the soul to have even memory - although CR implies it does.

With complete relativity, the question is not whether one has a soul, rather, which organism will be interpreted as the soul? One could then introduce orders and even interpret the brain as the soul, of 1st order - in example.

And the human organism obviously has the ability to read this memory through the cascade of organisms between the brain and the soul and then match it with experiences of the brain.

Therefore, rendering of soul memories can be very accurate, providing there's no significant loss, or lack, of information (either in soul's memory or brain's experience), in which case some of rendered experience might appear blank.

5 Affinity in soul-body coupling

If coupling of bodies and souls is understood as symbiosis (even if asymmetric one) there must be some affinity of the soul toward certain characteristics of the body.

If coupling occurs at [or about the] time of conception, these should be the genetically encoded characteristics.

And these characteristics should be more or less shared between different incarnations (difference should, due to evolution, change with time).

In humans, affinity should be strongest or direct toward the characteristics of the brain, while other affinities may be weaker or indirect (in example, coupling with a bigger brain might indirectly result in coupling with a less pronounced body of the individual - or indirect coupling with a specific metabolism).

Strong affinity is also likely to be present toward characteristics of fluids in the brain such as blood type (15% - 20% of the body's blood is in the brain).

The level of affinity, in general, could be determined by evaluating the necessity of survival of specific organs for the survival of distinct individual consciousness, however this is also likely to correlate with distance from the primary organ (brain).

Some species have multiple brains (even in humans, the enteric nervous system formed by nerve cells lining the gastrointestinal tract can be interpreted as a second brain) and different organs might have brain equivalents on their own. This is not surprising if organs in an organism are post-cursors of symbiosis of different organisms, it is however, expected that apart from the primary brain where distinct individual consciousness is located other brains will be subdued.

There are, therefore, multiple souls in a body of an individual organism, differing by the amount of consciousness and, by evaluating affinity of the [primary] soul toward specific organs, one is also evaluating affinity of the primary soul toward *secondary* souls.

In some species, distinct consciousness of the individual might be low and brain might not be a vital organ required for the survival of the body and its

ecosystem.

Leeches, for example, have many roughly equal brains (at least between the head and tail brain). In that case, with death of primary soul, a secondary soul could become primary. However, if differences between brains are low, competition (or lack of leadership) could decrease the lifespan of the collective.

Brain (at least as we know it) is not necessary for soul/body coupling though.

Sponges, which seem to have lost the brain over evolution, still have genetic components of synapses[21] (post-synaptic density or PSD proteins) so [with affinity to particular DNA] souls are still coupling with these animals, even though their consciousness (coupling?) is low and decreasing from larval stage to adulthood.

But not even these are necessary for soul/body coupling. Microbes, fungi and plants also have some consciousness and in these cases, soul is coupling to DNA that may have nothing to do with a brain. Perhaps the reason why some fungi tend to occupy [and take over] brains of other animals is to increase their own consciousness on this scale (coupling or entanglement with the body of *matter*) - even if they are doing it *unconsciously*. In that case, soul of a fungi is, after all, coupling with a brain, albeit indirectly in time.

It seems that, if there is no affinity of souls toward brains in space, there is in time.

Even if they don't have brains on their own - microbes, fungi and plants do work in symbiosis, forming functional neural network equivalents. Why? Unless they all form a part of a larger [extremely introverted] organism whose consciousness is mentally affecting these, guiding them to form its own synapses (see definition of life in CR).

By comparing these synapses with our own one can learn that this is a symbiotic relationship - our brain cells don't consciously exchange information to form (or mirror) our thoughts, it benefits them as well. The activity of the brain is thus a synchronicity of physical and mental activity.

Destruction of forests might be decreasing consciousness (and increasing probability of death) of the planet and could certainly be interpreted as a disease working against the planet, however, as I have hypothesized elsewhere, this is likely just a part of its development process - extinction of life is limited to surface and *synapses* on surface are probably just precursors to real synapses that exist deep below the surface.

However, planting trees (sustainably) and working for the planet (living in symbiosis with) rather than against it should lead to long-term benefits (as it does for microbes, fungi and plants) - even though one might be mentally guided to do so.

5.1 Vertical affinity

A soul may change vertical energy level, when it will couple with different species of the body. In fact, I hypothesize that (since both, *massive* photons and neutrinos should oscillate) soul oscillates between different species regularly and there will be affinity toward specific characteristics of species - most likely mass (energy).

6 Synchronized evolution

Each living being has a personal space which is theoretically unlimited but effectively constrained by other bodies. For Earth, this would be the Hill sphere.

As this space extends well beyond the visible body, an individual can affect and be affected by phenomena some distance away. However entities may also be directly and indirectly connected through channels of entanglement of some scale.

Feelings, personalities and evolution of people can thus be synchronized.

But this synchronization also occurs, due to vertical oscillation, between different scales of energy. In events of strong evolution when one scale (living the future) expands while the other (living the past) collapses, gravitational waves are emitted leaving behind imprints (echoes) of future and past.

These echoes can then provide guidance in evolution and may even be recognized and interpreted as signs or signals of synchronicity.

7 Conclusion

I have a lot of experience with synchronicity, it has also been proven that physical processes in the body can be significantly and consciously affected by the mind. Some achieve it through meditation (which may be described as practice of introversion), but it can also be achieved without meditation (I am one evidence for that, having succeeded in controlling diseases by my mind, but others have done it too).

There's a lot of logic for the existence of a soul, its karma and reincarnation. Yet, all these phenomena are not well studied or not studied at all in modern science.

I believe this is because majority of people is polarized and does not have the ability to mentally affect the body (at least not consciously) - presenting problems with replication. They also do not have a sense for synchronicity and lack imagination. But the underlying reason for all this would have to be biased thoughts - lack of symmetry in brain operation, and optimization for short-term profit, rendering their inability to even consider a possibility for the existence of higher power in mentality or its long-term conservation.

It seems that mainstream science has chosen the path of strongly physical (material) interactions - a short-term *safe* path, with fast rewards (points, grades, careers and money).

This... is sad.

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